

IMPROVING THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL QUALITIES OF CADETS, THE ACADEMY OF THE ARMED FORCES SPECIFIC ASPECTS

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Annotation: In this article, from a scientific and practical point of view, the spiritual development of future officers is justified. And also, the goals and objectives of the ongoing work and measures taken are scientifically considered based on the concept of increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in the system of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: spirituality, spiritual perfection, national army, nation, personality, human activity, ethical ideal, education and upbringing, feat, good goal, exactingness, intellectual potential.

The role and importance of youth spirituality in the development of society is very great. Every person living in society should strive for his great future to serve the motherland with his beliefs, goals and interests. In the Basic Law of our country, the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan are established to protect state sovereignty and territorial integrity, the peaceful life and security of the population. Therefore, in the effective implementation of these tasks, it is important to regularly continue the process of developing new laws, other regulatory documents that will help to form a professional and mobilizing National Army that will reliably ensure the security of our country, peace and tranquility of our people. In this regard, special attention is paid to the Organization of an effective system for training highly qualified officer personnel at the Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the necessary knowledge, abilities and skills, high combat and moral qualities, capable of adequately protecting their homeland. After all, today "the education of high professional, military and patriotic duty loyal, dedicated and mercenary military personnel is one of the most important conditions for the protection of the independence and territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [1].

Of these, it is known that the spirituality of a high nation and the future of a state can be great. Zero T.As Mahmudov noted: "spirituality is a universal vision that encompasses the entire human activities and ideals of the nation and the individual... Spirituality is the world of spiritual perception that expresses the "intelligent heart" of the individual and the nation, whose sides are manifested by the presumption of history, which expresses the degree of humanization of Nature, Society and Man"[2].

Future officers studying at the Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan should know that they are citizens of their country, educate their will and courage, purposefulness, goodness and exactingness, strive to show creativity in studies, art, any work. They must have a complete understanding of the material and spiritual world, spiritual and spiritual feed. They should also know that together with their people they are responsible for

the renewal of society, the increase in social wealth, the peace and tranquility of the country; behave, be demanding towards those around them, love the spiritual wealth of their people, progressive culture around the world, be internationalists and loyal friends, be able to see innovation in labor, beauty in art, spiritual beauty in They must deeply understand and strive for the future of their homeland that it is its decisive, invincible power, and in order to become an invincible force, a high spirituality must be formed in them.

Cadets of the Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan should show a lively interest in everything and events that are relevant to their homeland, be socially active, be updated in society, increase in social wealth, care for the prosperity, peace and tranquility of the country, increase in their personal contribution; be loyal to the motherland and friendship, stabilize the qualities of Therefore, systematic practical work (round tables, meetings, artistic literary and other various evenings, workshop sessions, promotions, quizzes, spiritual-educational and cultural activities) is carried out in the academy system, providing a solid military discipline, a healthy spiritual and moral environment in the units, aimed at educating military personnel with high combat, mobilization training and professional skills, always being a thing for the protection of After all, the development of any society, its level in one or another time and space, largely depends on the spirituality of citizens, lifestyle, spiritual and material, social needs of people and to what extent they are satisfied. After all, "spirituality," writes A.Erkaev is the inner (mental) intellectual and fixed emotional (non-rational) world of the nation, formed over the centuries, whose roots are inextricably linked with its historical experiences and social cultural development"[3].

Looking at the process of historical development of the human way of life, high morale was one of the main factors of the development of society in any situation, and its further stabilization is directly related to the fundamental turn that takes place in the country, and understanding its content is important for all, based on national values, to follow it From this point of view, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Supreme Commander-In-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that the following problems exist in the system of radical improvement of the system of raising the spiritual and educational level of military personnel:

In the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, systemic problems still persist in the issues of instilling the vital and professional skills of military personnel in their hearts and minds on the basis of knowledge, increasing their knowledge in harmony with Real socio-political changes in the life of our country, approaching socio-political processes taking place in our

In particular, in higher military educational institutions, the necessary infrastructures for the training of officers with a wide worldview and range of thinking in the spiritual and educational direction and the spiritual and educational and cultural sphere in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan do not meet the requirements of the time.

In the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a system of effective cooperation with state and public organizations has not been created in the organization of spiritual and educational work. Work with the families of military personnel, studying and solving their problems is not set to the proper level[4].

The fact that our country is becoming more and more deeply integrated into the world community, our people's desire to get a place among the developed nations of the world requires the development of material and economic factors, as well as high

technologies, spiritual factors. But the development of both groups of factors itself depends on the growth of human thinking, on the strengthening of creative potential. In the process of deepening radical reforms, some backward concepts left over from the past in the social consciousness, vices of administrative command, the slow dissolution of immortality moods or the influence of destructive, foreign ideas on some young people, the lack of ideological immunity increase the relevance of the issue of freedom of thought. Therefore, the following are the main tasks of the concept of improving the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in the system of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

building a unified system aimed at raising the spiritual level and intellectual potential of military personnel and the formation of a worldview based on our rich culture, long-standing values and traditions;

deep instill in the mind of military personnel the feeling that the protection of the Motherland is an honorable and sacred duty, pride in our national army, responsibility for protecting the security of the state;

to systematically and consistently convey to military personnel the socio-economic reforms carried out in our country, the legislation adopted, the content and essence of state programs, and to form a conscious attitude and active life position in them in relation to the globalization processes taking place in the world and around us, to increase feelings of loyalty, responsibility, dedication to duty;

based on the study and analysis of the historical roots of our national heritage, the widespread promotion of the instructive life of our great ancestors and brave contemporaries, who showed heroism in the path of freedom of the motherland, military personnel were taught that "the people of Uzbekistan will never depend on anyone!" to decide on a life belief;

these include instilling traditions of goodness and compassion in military personnel through thoughtful disclosure of the true essence of religion, forming humanistic and benevolent relationships, and educating them on the basis of respect and respect for our national culture and values, dedication and loyalty, honesty and purity, independent thought and a healthy lifestyle, etc[5].

At the same time, it should be noted that due to the concept of improving the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in the system of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the modern system of education and training for the promotion of knowledge and experience of cadets of the Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been established. In fact, this system today allows future officers not only to improve their skills, theoretical and practical knowledge, but also provides them with ample opportunities for experience and skill in future combat service activities. In addition, a new "concept of moral and spiritual supply of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [6] was developed.

In turn, the work of training and training future officers requires further improvement of a completely new educational-technical and spiritual-moral system, which provides for the formation of personnel who are thinking in a new way, loyal to their homeland, people and country. In our eyes, spirituality is considered an important factor leading a nation to progress, increasing the power of the state. Because where, in which country there is spirituality, in the same place, there will be no place for such negative vices as ignorance, greed, negligence, selfishness, sloth, manliness, teakiness, invisibility, evil, slander.

From this point of view, it is important to divide our national and spiritual values into the main types and teach them as spiritual qualities, which serve as the basis for raising the spiritual maturity of cadets of the Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The transformation of spirituality into a material force in the daily activities of future officers is manifested first of all in their behavior, in their attitude towards their family, nationality and homeland.

The scientific and creative competition between them is of great importance in the pursuit of the interest of prospective officers in knowledge. This competition is further sharpened in the course of the lesson, scientific circle meetings, scientific-theoretical, scientific-practical meetings and examinations and Olympiads with different degrees and directions, which gives cadets an incentive to research. In this regard, effective work is carried out in the academy system. But it is necessary to instill in them more modernity and demand, a spirit of creativity. This competition should go out of state, the youth of the country should also demonstrate their scientific potential in international audiences as national pride and pride. After all, today "...despite the measures taken, the system of training military personnel does not fully meet the requirements of the time. ...we have not created modern conditions in military educational institutions to the Lord. ...On the contrary, it is necessary that our cadets and listeners have the most advanced, innovative knowledge and skills in the field of Education. Here is our main goal " [7].

In increasing the social activity of prospective officers, it is considered important to involve them more broadly in scientific research. Usually, the scientific search of students is carried out through scientific circles. In this regard, the Academy has accumulated a good positive experience in the system. But today it is important to associate this direction with grants, publish separate grants for the scientific research of cadets, create separate programs that cadets must fulfill in the agreements of the departments with systems related to the military sphere, form scientific research programs that they themselves lead. In our view, this process should begin with the initial lessons of cadets in the first year. He must determine his future scientific activity, create his own scientific program with the help of the department, where his specialty is focused, as early as the first year. From this, their relationship with organizations and scientific research institutions is formed.

The penetration of cadets into scientific research work according to their own interests is an absolute difference from his involvement in scientific research. The scientific creative activity formulated for the current report, which sometimes occurs, is far from giving positive results. An important place in increasing the social activity of Cadets is occupied by the modern educational and educational system and production integration established in the Academy. In this integration, on the one hand, the fundamental reforms carried out in education, on the other hand, the processes of modernization carried out in production make such demands on each other, as a result, the portfolio of these requirements, on the one hand, further perfection of the military education system, increasing its effectiveness, further clarifying the target indicator, and on the other, on

In conclusion, each new stage of the development of society is characterized by the emergence of a new era even in the spiritual maturation of people. Just as there is no society without spirituality that is just, capable of promotion, there cannot be spirituality without society. The problems that exist in the economic, socio-political spheres of society can be solved by raising morale, relying on it. From this it can be said that the development of spiritual and moral

qualities in cadets of the Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan is strictly related to deciding how loyal they are to their national-historical, cultural heritage.

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